

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Triyandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol. XIV, Book. III -IV

JULY - DECEMBER 2022

SRF

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohanam

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohanam@gmail.com

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Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumarcs@gmail.com

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Analytical study of Śabda

Dr.N.S.Sharmila¹

Abstract

The word śabda has been used in different senses in different contexts to mean 'something'. But all the systems of thought agree in this basic point that śravaṇendriya' is the sense-organ responsible for perceiving śabda". According to Patanjali, 'Śabda' basically means sound or dhvani . In the opinion of Linguists, the word 'śabda' is used to signify a pada or word. This pada consists of certain letter or varṇas". Among the different systems of Indian Philosophy, except Cārvāka, Bauddha and Vaiśeṣika, almost all the important schools have been recognized śabda as a separate pramāṇa.

Key words

Śabda, dhvani, auditory sense-organ, syntax, āptavākya, Verbal cognition, Phoneme, Conceptualisation

Introduction

In our world, different people have been using the word 'śabda' in different senses in different contexts to mean 'something'. Here the word 'something' may be an object, an emotion, an event, a command or a question. But all the systems of thought agree in this basic point that śravaṇendriya' is the sense-organ responsible for perceiving śabda. On the basis of this, we can say that

- (a) In a wide sense or very broadly understood, 'śabda' means sound or dhvani of any kind which is perceived by the auditory sense- organ".
- (b) In a restricted sense, 'Śabda' means uttered or written strings of words having a syntax and meaning. In short it means language. Here Śabda is used to denote a spoken word or pada which signifies something like the word 'gauḥ' which signifies an animal having a dewlap, a tail, hoofs, horns etc.

1 Associate Professor, Dept.of Sahithya, Govt.Sanskrit College, Tripunithura

- (c) In a still more restricted sense, 'śabda' is used in the sense of a sentence spoken by a reliable person or āptavākya which is taken as authority or testimony. This śabda has been recognised to be the means of Verbal Cognition (Śābdabodha).

Analysis of Sabda – Different Views

According to Patanjali, 'Śabda' basically means sound or dhvani. In the opinion of Linguists, the word 'śabda' is used to signify a pada or word. This pada consists of certain letter or varṇas.

The word śabda is translated as speech by some while some others translated as word. Sometimes the word authority is also used as a synonym for śabda.

Mīmāṃsakas describe this Śabda as an eternal substance (nitya dravya) while in contrast, the Naiyāyikas describe it as an attribute of Ākāśa and understand it as anitya (impermanent). According to the Nyāya- Vaiśeṣikas, Śabda, the sound is the specific or differentiating quality (Vaiśeṣika Guṇa) of Ākāśa.

Śabda can be explained etymologically in Sanskrit as the sequence of letters or phonemes from which meaning is sounded or bursted forth¹¹. For eg- 'cow'. Here the sequence of letters or phonemes such as cow, from which the meaning of an individual such as cow, a form such as dewlap, tail, horn etc and the generic property such as the cowness is sounded or bursted forth. So we can say that cow is a word.

In Modern Linguistics, word (śabda or pada) is understood generally to be any segment of sentence bounded by successive points at which pausing (potential or actual) is possible. Such a word is recognised as a part of speech conveying an idea or meaning partly or fully.

The word 'śabda' again is technically used in the school of Nyāya in the sense of a pramāṇavākya. A sentence is undoubtedly a specific collection of words. So, a sentence is inevitably a special collection of sounds ie. mutually related articulate sounds. This śabda in its basic character of dhvani is a guṇa (quality) and not a dravya (substance).

In the opinion of Gautama- āptopadeśaḥ śabdaḥ ie as a statement of a trustworthy person. According to Annambhatta 'Āptavākyaṃ

Śabdah' ; testimony is a statement of a trustworthy person. Here āpta is sometimes described as an authoritative person or a person having expert knowledge in a given field.

But for Bhartṛhari, Śabda means something more than language. It is the name of a complex phenomenon implying an activity as well as a principle. As a type of activity, it is something in which all human beings, in fact, all sentient beings are engaged. The Sanskrit term for it is Śabdana vyāpāra. B.K. Matilal translates it as languageing.

Again as a principle, śabda stands for the very potency for communicating thoughts through language. It is the linguistic potency, the very power of conceptualisation, which is the basis of our consciousness as well as the awareness of the external world. This potency itself is śabdatattva, the word principle. This śabdatattva, being the central concept of all forms of phenomenal activity, is identified with the Brahman. Because Bhartṛhari conceives the word principle as the basic principle of consciousness as well as the awareness of the existence of objects which are characterised by names and forms. He further conceives this reality to be without beginning and end (anādi nidhanam) meaning all our cognitive episodes about our inner states of mind as well as the external world are sequential in nature(krama). Also Bhartṛhari defines the objects as 'śabdopagrahi'. It implies that objects of our thought are word-determined. Be it perception, inference or any other method, whenever we cognise objects or external reality, we always do so in terms of names. Without names they are unidentifiable, hence not knowable. In short, without language or śabda, these objects cannot be understood .

Concept of Śabda as a Pramāṇa

Śabdapramāṇa means the linguistic method of obtaining knowledge (both oral and written); and is distinctively different from the other methods of knowledge. Unlike the methods of perception, inference etc. facts and sense objects do not form the basis of such knowledge; but its object is language itself. The term Śabdapramāṇa is very often translated as 'verbal authority'. Which tends to shift the emphasis from the linguistic aspect to the 'authoritative' aspect of

the theory. But different schools of Indian philosophy have different views about this Śabdapramāṇa. Among the different systems of Indian Philosophy, except Cārvāka, Bauddha and Vaiśeṣika, almost all the important schools have been recognized śabda as a separate pramāṇa.

Analysis of śabda strengthens different systems of thought in different ways. Nyāya provides the Indian mind a powerful tool to examine what is wrong and what is right to solve many basic philosophico-logical problems concerning the nature of knowledge, form of knowledge and the philosophy of language.

While Prācīna Nyāya trains the Indian mind to tackle philosophical issues; Navya Nyāya provides and develops powerful tools to develop ambiguity-free discourse.

In the opinion of V .N. Jha, the system of Nyāya- Vaiśeṣika should be viewed and studied as an analytic system of human behavior, because its prime concern has been analysis of human behavior. Nyāya school of philosophy opines that 'nihśreyasa' or 'apavarga' can be attained through knowledge only. This knowledge is based on language or sentence. Therefore by analysing the sentence and exactly pointing out the meaning of a sentence, one can be led towards the path of truth.

The greatest contribution that the Nyāya system has made is in teaching that nothing is to be taken for granted by closing one's eyes but everything should be accepted with open eyes. No authority is higher than logic. The Nyāya system teaches us how to organize our thoughts into a structured whole and it helps us to overcome emotion and how to give a logical foundation to our thinking.

In the opinion of Jayantabbatta, the origin of Nyāyaśāstra is to clarify the confusions created by those who did not have faith in the Vedic wisdom. Right from the beginning, the system of Nyāya Vaiśeṣika has provided a perspective to think rationally. The origin and growth of the Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika system is through its logical frame-work.

The greatest contribution of Nyāya- Vaiśeṣika is its development of a framework for argument. It presents a tool which is used by

almost all systems- Mīmāṃsa, Vedānta, sāmkhya, Vyākaraṇa, Alankāraśāstra etc. In other words it trains us to think rationally. Nyāya deals with neither unknown things nor with definitely known things, but only with those that are doubtful.

It is very much useful in developing the powers of logical thinking for the scholars. It finally avers that all knowledge of which one can be conscious is determinate and indeterminate knowledge is only a logical presupposition. Likewise the treatment of śabda in Mīmāṃsa makes a solid contribution to the Indian theory of meaning. This is the first system to undertake the analysis of a sentence and its meaning systematically. It has contributed much to the development of Linguistics, especially semantics by proposing various theories of verbal cognition.

The theories of the correlation of the expressed or Abhihitānvayavāda and the expression of the correlated or Anvitābhidhānavada have drawn the attention of Western Scholars to a great extent. This view is accepted by the Naiyāyikas and the Vedantins as well. The term 'Mīmāṃsa' which occurs in the Taittirīya Samhita, Chāndogyopaniṣad etc. means arriving at a certain decision after considering all the pros and cons about something in question. The aim of the Mīmāṃsa system is to show each and every sentence, each and every word and each and every syllable of the Veda is meaningful and purposeful by interpreting the Vedas each and every sentence if meaningfully. This is the reason why Mīmāṃsa is basically a science of sentence interpretation and bears the names like Vākyaśāstra, Vākyaṛthaśāstra quite significantly.

In Western Philosophy, Philosophy of Language becomes a point of discussion only after Frege, Russell and Wittgenstein i.e. during the last 100-125 years or so. But the Mīmāṃsa system has been dealing with this topic for not less than 2000 years.

Main contribution of Mīmāṃsa in the field of verbal understanding can be stated in just two words: 'ananyalabhyah śabdārthah' i.e. the meaning of the word is not obtainable from anything else than the word.

Similarly the main aim of the philosophy of grammar is to

know the reality, the base of the universe or the Śabda Braḥman. The sphoṭa doctrine of Bhartṛhari is quite a significant contribution which is both solid and fundamental at once. It is only on the basis of the theories of Bhartṛhari, Ānandavardhana developed the theory of suggestion or Dhvani-Sidhānta. Bhartṛhari maintains that it is through Vyākaraṇa that śabda- Braḥman known and therefore Mokṣa is attained.

Conclusion

In short , according to the philosophy of grammar, śabda is the most significant tattva. What Bhartṛhari says in this regard is very significant- Just as the light which is in the fire stick acts as the cause of further lights, the word which is in the mind is the cause of the uttered sound. It is Indian grammar, especially Paninian grammar, that lays the solid foundation for the analysis of a sentence and its meaning.

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KIRANĀVALĪ
Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation
The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XIV.
Book III-IV
JULY – DECEMBER 2022

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram-36
Sanskritresearchfoundation@gmail.com